

Research paper

Intelligent condition monitoring of power cables using advanced machine learning models

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ABSTRACT

Power cables are susceptible to ageing phenomena, which can lead to unexpected failures and catastrophic damage. Consequently, investigating the degradation of power cables and predicting their health condition is crucial for avoiding irreversible destruction, power delivery stoppage, and power quality problems in power systems. This paper offers an intelligent health monitoring framework that uses advanced machine learning (ML) techniques for various power cables, which is trained and validated on a new dataset of 15 kV and 20 kV cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) power cables, incorporating features such as partial discharge, age, visual inspection, and neutral corrosion. To identify the most effective algorithm, 18 ML techniques were systematically benchmarked, with hyperparameters for each model tuned via Bayesian optimisation to ensure a fair comparison. The results indicate that boosting-based models consistently outperform linear, tree-based, and neural network-based models, achieving accuracies higher than 98 %. Furthermore, the framework's generalisation capabilities are tested on a new dataset of a different cable, i.e., 138 kV ethylene propylene rubber (EPR) power cables, showcasing high F1-scores exceeding 98 % in identifying health indexes. Finally, to evaluate its robustness under realistic imperfections, the framework was subjected to challenging stress test scenarios—including multi-feature missing measurements and severe class imbalance—demonstrating the CatBoost model's high resilience with accuracies consistently above 95 % for XLPE and above 75 % for EPR power cables. The proposed framework forms the core of intelligent, automated systems for condition-based asset management in modern electric network. By predicting a reliable health index for both new and existing assets, it serves as a robust tool for optimising capital-intensive expansion planning, network reconfiguration, and maintenance scheduling. Ultimately, this validated framework could serve as the foundation for developing a digital twin for power cables, enabling a shift from reactive maintenance to predictive, intelligent asset management.

1. Introduction

The integration of renewable energy sources and distributed generation into modern power systems, along with ever-increasing load demand and network reconfiguration, has underscored the critical role of power cables in ensuring reliable electricity transmission and distribution [1–3]. Power cables are significant assets within the power network, and their safe operation is essential for grid stability, playing a role in 81.1 % of medium voltage power faults [1]. A major factor influencing cable health is the condition of its insulation materials. The degradation of insulation materials like cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) and ethylene propylene rubber (EPR) is a substantial cause of cable failure. Although designed for a service life of 30 to 40 years, [2,4],

continuous assessment of insulation condition is a central concern for power system maintenance and reliability [2]. A general structure of power cables is shown in Fig. 1. Cable ageing is a gradual and largely irreversible deterioration of cable materials over time, especially insulation, leading to impaired serviceability and increasing failure rates [1, 5]. This phenomenon, recognised as a primary security risk to systems, results from the cumulative and often synergistic effects of various stresses [6]. These include electrical stresses (such as operating and transient voltages, partial discharges (PD), and space charge accumulation) [1,2,5,7,8], thermal stresses (due to conductor current, dielectric and eddy current losses, high current events, and ambient temperature fluctuations) [6,9], mechanical stresses (including bending, tension, pressure, torsion, repeated compression, load cycles, improper handling, transportation, and bedding practices) [10,11], and environmental

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Nomenclature table

Abbreviation

AFN	Adaptive fusion networks	GA	Genetic algorithm
AI	Artificial intelligence	GB	Gradient boosting
ANFIS	Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system	GRNN	General regression neural network
ANN	Artificial neural network	HistGBC	Histogram-based gradient boosting classifier
AO	Aquila optimiser	KNN	K-nearest neighbours
BO	Bayesian optimisation	LightGBM	Light gradient-boosting machine
BP	Backpropagation	LR	Logistic regression
CatBoost	Categorical boosting	ML	Machine learning
CEATI	Centre for energy advancement through technological innovation	NB	Naïve Bayes
CFNN	Cascade-forward neural network	NC	Neutral corrosion
CI	Confidence interval	PD	Partial discharge
CNN	Convolutional neural network	PDP	Partial dependence plot
DSOs	Distribution system operators	PSO	Particle swarm optimisation
DT	Decision tree	RF	Random forest
ECE	Expected calibration error	SCM	Subtractive clustering method
EPR	Ethylene propylene rubber	SGD	Stochastic gradient descent
Extra Trees	Extremely randomised trees	SVM	Support vector machine
FFNN	Feedforward neural network	TSOs	Transmission system operators
FSVM	Fuzzy support vector machine	VI	Visual inspection
		WT	Wavelet transform
		XGBoost	Extreme gradient boosting
		XLPE	Cross-linked polyethylene

Fig. 1. The general cross-section and structure of a typical medium-voltage power cable, illustrating the different layers including conductor, semi-conducting screens, insulation (XLPE/EPR), metallic screen, and outer sheath.

factors (such as humidity, sunlight exposure, corrosive chemicals, and microbiological effects in soil) [12,13].

The effects of ageing on insulation materials are profound, as it deteriorates dielectric performance, reducing overall insulation capabilities [1] and increasing parameters such as cable capacitance, dielectric loss, and leakage current [4]. This degradation can lead to the formation of water trees (microcavities resulting from moisture and electrical stress) [14] and electrical trees (gas-filled channels originating from contaminants or stress enhancements) [15], both of which weaken the insulation and can culminate in breakdown [16]. As a result, PD activities start within the insulation and chemically degrade and erode the material. The detection of PD is therefore considered a primary method for assessing cable health [17,18]. Furthermore, ageing induces physicochemical changes such as oxidation, chain scission, crosslinking, and alterations in material properties like crystallinity and melting point [19]. These changes make polymers like polyethylene vulnerable to cracking and embrittlement and can also change the mechanical properties of materials [11,20].

Traditional power cable assessment has relied on off-line diagnostic

methods such as very low frequency dielectric strength testing [21], DC high potential [22], dissipation factor [23], time and frequency domain reflectometry [24,25], dielectric response analysis [26], frequency response analysis [27], and insulation resistance testing [28]. All require the cable circuit to be de-energised and re-powered by an external source, making them ex-situ and destructive tests. Statistical analysis of historical failure and operational data using models such as the Weibull distribution [11], as well as routine maintenance, visual inspections, and expert judgement, have also been used for condition evaluation [29]. However, off-line tests often apply voltages exceeding rated levels, accelerating insulation ageing or causing damage, while requiring costly outages [2]. As a result, using such static and periodic diagnostic methods cannot reflect real-time operating status or the dynamic thermal and electrical conditions experienced during normal operation in real-life [1]. Furthermore, methods relying solely on historical or single-source data provide only overall failure rate predictions, failing to account for environmental influences or accurately determine the condition of specific individual cable segments [30]. The dependence of these traditional methods on expert experience can introduce subjectivity and struggling with identifying insulation status or handling the complex, non-linear problems inherent in cable ageing [6]. This creates a significant practical challenge for utilities: how to non-intrusively identify the specific health condition of thousands of cable segments to prevent failures and optimise maintenance. Thus, the traditional strategies are ineffective and costly for managing ageing, leading to frequent unexpected failures and high maintenance expenses.

Given the inherent drawbacks of traditional ageing analysis methods, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques offer a powerful alternative for power network management [4], including for online monitoring [31], capturing real-time operational data and bypassing the need for costly and potentially damaging off-line tests [32–34]. In comparison with traditional statistical models that provide only overall failure rates, ML can integrate various data sources—from real-time sensors to historical records—to provide more precise, asset-specific predictions while accounting for complex environmental factors. By processing vast amounts of data and modelling complex nonlinear relationships, AI-driven algorithms can automatically extract features, predict equipment degradation, and identify potential failures with high accuracy, enabling a critical shift from reactive

repairs to proactive, predictive maintenance strategies that significantly enhance system reliability and reduce costs [35].

Recent studies increasingly apply ML to power cable condition monitoring using various data modalities and model types. For example, ultra-high-frequency radio frequency identification-based temperature measurements have been analysed using general regression neural network (GRNN) models [36], while power line communication channel frequency response data have been evaluated using random forest (RF) and support vector machines (SVM) for anomaly detection [37]. Similarly, HVDC PD patterns have been classified using SVM [38], and operational parameters such as voltage and current have been utilised with artificial neural networks (ANN) architectures [39]. Despite their contributions, many of these studies focus on specific degradation modalities or feature types [36,39], or employ limited algorithmic diversity without benchmarking across heterogeneous model families (e.g., boosting, neural networks, linear models) under consistent hyperparameter optimisation [37,38]. Furthermore, while interpretability constraints have been acknowledged for complex models [40], there remains a need for physically grounded validation strategies to enhance trust in ML-driven diagnostics [41]. Addressing these gaps, including the development of models suitable for integration into digital twin frameworks for comprehensive, real-time asset health assessment, is essential for developing robust, generalisable, and field-deployable condition monitoring systems; accordingly, recent advances in ML-based health classification have evolved through multiple phases of model development and optimisation [42–44].

Building on these advantages, the classification of power cable health condition has progressed from traditional statistical. Initial applications included decision trees (DT) [45], followed by SVMs [46], whose limitations in handling nonlinear ageing phenomena brought their integration with particle swarm optimisation (PSO) for hyperparameter tuning [47] and extensions such as Fuzzy SVM combined with the relief-F algorithm for feature selection [9]. In addition, ensemble methods including RF [48,49], k-nearest neighbours (KNN) [46], extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), and categorical boosting (CatBoost) were later adopted, with performance improvements achieved through hybrid optimisation techniques such as PSO-enhanced XGBoost [6] and CatBoost combined with the Aquila optimiser (AO) [50]. Regarding neural network-based models, notably ANN and their genetic algorithm-enhanced ANN [14,51,52], were applied to life prediction but remained constrained by high data requirements, susceptibility to overfitting, and limited interpretability. More recent advances have focused on hybrid and ensemble strategies, exemplified by adaptive fusion networks (AFN) integrating sensor data and visual ratings [53] and ensembles combining SVM, XGBoost, RF, and KNN to improve insulation health classification. Despite these advancements, limitations remain for the practical deployment of these models, as existing studies have not rigorously tested generalisation to entirely new cable types, nor demonstrated robustness against the imbalanced and incomplete data common in real-world scenarios.

Addressing the identified needs for comprehensive benchmarking, rigorous generalisation testing, and validation under realistic data imperfections, transparent model interpretability, and reliable probabilistic calibration, this paper presents a benchmarking framework for ML models in power cable condition monitoring, established through the systematic evaluation of various algorithms, including neural network-based, tree-based, boosting-based, and linear models, with hyperparameters tuned using Bayesian optimisation and cross-validation techniques to ensure a fair and robust comparison. The models are benchmarked based on their performance on a novel combined dataset of 15 kV and 20 kV XLPE cables which is introduced in this paper for the first time. Then, the best models are selected and further evaluated on an entirely new dataset of 138 kV EPR power cables. Finally, the ML models' robustness is benchmarked under challenging scenarios, including significant class imbalance, to provide a thorough assessment of their practical capability. The proposed framework enables intelligent

health monitoring for various types and voltage levels of power cables, thereby facilitating the development of more efficient maintenance planning. The primary objective of this study is to develop and benchmark machine learning models for assessing the health index of power cables based on condition monitoring data. The secondary objectives are to evaluate the robustness of the proposed framework under incomplete and imbalanced data conditions and to analyse the interpretability of the learnt features to ensure transparency and operational trustworthiness. The main contributions of this paper are listed below:

- Establishment of a new performance benchmark on a novel dataset made out of combined data for 15 kV and 20 kV XLPE cables, demonstrating that optimised boosting models can achieve over 98 % accuracy.
- Framework's generalisation capabilities by validating it on a new 138 kV EPR power cable.
- Rigorous stability tests simulating missing sensor data and severely imbalanced datasets, demonstrating the framework's resilience and confirming its reliability for practical, imperfect operational environments.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: methodology in [Section 2](#) for the introduction of the entire framework with subsections regarding its different parts, such as the dataset, ML models, Bayesian optimiser, and evaluation metrics. Then, the results of the proposed framework have been presented in [Section 3](#), encompassing the prediction of health classes of new XLPE power cable, generalisation capability on the EPR dataset, missing measurement scenario, and the case of imbalanced classes. Finally, the findings of the paper are summarised in [Section 4](#) as a conclusion and future work.

2. Methodology

This study presents an intelligent framework for monitoring the health index of power cables, which encompasses several stages, ranging from dataset generation and preprocessing to predicting the health condition of new cables, as illustrated in the conceptual schematic in [Fig. 2](#). A dataset comprising samples from 15 kV and 20 kV XLPE power cables is used to train the ML models for condition monitoring. The key components of the entire system such as dataset, ML models, and optimisation algorithm are presented individually in following sections.

2.1. Datasets

The dataset used for training the ML models in this study is a new dataset consisted of combination of two separate datasets for 15 kV and 20 kV XLPE power cables with 2500 and 3943 samples, respectively [54, 55], providing 6443 samples in total. This combined dataset provides a broader and more diverse representation of operational conditions than previously available, creating a more challenging and realistic benchmark for evaluating model performance. As a consequence of combining these datasets, a new categorical feature has been created and included to the dataset indicating the level of voltage along with type of the cable. The final 6443 samples dataset has continuous features service life or age (15 - 56 years), PD (0.03 - 1), neutral corrosion (NC) (0.39 - 1), and loading current (50 - 700 A), and categorical features visual inspections (VI) (namely, poor, medium, and good), and the aforementioned cable type. The health status of the samples was determined using a health indexing methodology based on guidelines from the Centre for Energy Advancement through Technological Innovation (CEATI) Report No T134700-50/118 [54–56]. The features used in the dataset are based on the duration of reliable operation of each power cable, the localised dielectric breakdown, the damages recorded visually over years, the level of corrosion due to moisture and chemical exposure, and the maximum current carrying capability. The distribution of the power cables based on the health indexes is illustrated in [Fig. 3a](#), which shows

Fig. 2. The conceptual schematic of the proposed intelligent condition monitoring framework, illustrating the workflow from data input (Dataset features) through model training (condition monitoring with Bayesian optimisation and ML models) to performance evaluation (health prediction results).

Fig. 3. The distribution of the five health index labels (serious to no degradation) within the (a) new XLPE dataset and (b) the 138 kV EPR dataset.

the majority have fallen into degraded conditions. As mentioned, the health index refers to the status of power cables and is labelled between 1 and 5, corresponding to serious, significant, moderate, minor and no degradation, respectively.

A comparative assessment confirmed that the XLPE training and EPR external datasets were statistically compatible for cross-material evaluation. Both sets were derived using the same CEATI-based labelling protocol, ensuring consistency in health index assignment. Representative statistics demonstrated high similarity, with mean cable ages of 35.52 years (std = 13.38) for XLPE and 34.69 years (std = 13.16) for EPR, and normalised PD values of 0.42 (std = 0.32) and 0.51 (std = 0.31), respectively. As shown in Fig. 4, the distributions of key ageing indicators such as age and PD exhibited comparable ranges and central tendencies, confirming that the EPR dataset was sufficiently aligned with the XLPE feature space to allow a valid generalisation analysis.

On the other hand, the 138 kV EPR power cable with the same features has been selected for testing the ability to generalise of the proposed framework with 4606 cables' samples [57], distributed as shown in Fig. 3b according to health index. The key numerical features (Age, PD, NC, I) were used directly, as PD and NC were provided in a pre-normalised format [54,55], and the source datasets were complete, requiring no imputation for missing values. To prepare the data for the ML models, categorical input features (VI and Type) were converted into a numerical format using one-hot encoding. For the target variable, the ordinal health index labels were used directly for all tree-based and

Fig. 4. The comparison of key feature distributions between the XLPE and EPR datasets, illustrating the distribution of (top) Age and (bottom) PD, confirming comparable ranges and tendencies across both cable types.

boosting models, which can inherently process integer-based classes. Separately, for the NN-based models only, the categorical target variable was also one-hot encoded to align with the final SoftMax output layer [58]. The one-hot encoding used in this study is depicted in Fig. 5. To prevent data leakage, the combined XLPE dataset is split into training and testing with a ratio of 80/20 using the random split technique before any model training or optimisation was performed. The EPR dataset is then used as an independent, unseen test set for generalisation and extrapolation capabilities of the trained models.

2.2. Classifier models

In this part, different ML models used for condition monitoring of the understudied power cables have been introduced. These 18 ML models are as follows: RF, XGBoost, CatBoost, Stochastic gradient descent classifier (SGDClassifier), logistic regression (LR), DT, extremely randomised trees (Extra Trees), adaptive boosting (AdaBoost), gradient boosting (GB), light gradient-boosting machine (LightGBM), histogram-based gradient boosting classifier (HistGBC), feedforward neural network (FFNN), cascade-forward neural network (CFNN), GRNN, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) with subtractive clustering method (SCM), KNN, naïve Bayes (NB) and SVM have also been implemented for the sake of comparison. Due to the results obtained through optimisation, the best models with the highest accuracy are the RF, XGBoost, and CatBoost, which are presented here in full detail. For more details about the architecture of other models, refer to Appendix 1.

2.2.1. RF classifier model

The RF model is a supervised ML model for both classification and regression tasks. The RF model is based on multiple trees and its operation is based on the basics of ensemble learning, providing better accuracy by increasing the number of trees for most of cases. The pseudo-code of RF algorithm is shown in Table 1 in Appendix 2. The most important hyperparameters selected for the RF classifier used in this study are the number of trees, the fraction of main dataset given to each tree and the number of features chosen at each split [59].

2.2.2. XGBoost classifier model

XGBoost model is one of the significant advancements among gradient boosting algorithm, integrating multiple DTs in series to get the highest accuracy [60]. It integrates regularisation, shrinkage and efficient optimisation strategies to improve scalability and robustness based on the following regularised function [60]:

$$\mathcal{L}(\psi) = \sum_{i=1, \in S}^n \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{x=1}^{n_estimators} \Omega(f_x) \quad (1)$$

where $\Omega(f_k) = \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \mu \sum_{j=1}^T \omega_j^2$ is refer to regularisation term and $\ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i)$ is the loss function between actual and predicted classes, and $T \leq 2^{max_depth}$, ω_j , γ and μ are number leaves, weight of j^{th} leaf, and

		One-hot code				
		1	2	4	4	5
Health Indexes	1	1	0	0	0	0
	2	0	1	0	0	0
	3	0	0	1	0	0
	4	0	0	0	1	0
	5	0	0	0	0	1

Fig. 5. The one-hot encoding method used for handling health indexes.

regularisation terms. The training subset (S) is controlled by the sub-sample ratio, and each tree uses a fraction of features determined by `colsample_bytree`. Splits are allowed only if the sum of Hessians in a leaf exceeds `min_child_weight`. The training of the model can be obtained through first and second derivatives of loss function with respect to predictions as $\xi_i = \frac{\partial \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{y}_i}$ and $\zeta_i = \frac{\partial^2 \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{y}_i^2}$, respectively. The predictions are determined by summing the contributions of all trees as follows, scaled by the learning rate (η) [60]:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{x=1}^{n_estimators} \eta f_x(x_i) \quad (2)$$

The XGBoost classifier has been utilised with a set of hyperparameters, optimised via Bayesian optimisation techniques. The hyperparameters used in the model are `n_estimators`, `max_depth`, `subsample`, `colsample_bytree`, `min_child_weight`, `gamma`, and `eta`. The schematic of XGBoost classifier is illustrated in Fig. 6.

2.2.3. CatBoost classifier model

CatBoost is another advance gradient boosting classifier that utilises binary DTs as base learners [61]. Considering following as training data [61],

$$D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1, \dots, n}, \quad x_i = (x_i^1, \dots, x_i^m) \quad (3)$$

The aim is to find a function, h , to minimise the expected loss ($J(h) = E_{x,y}[\Lambda(y, h(x))]$), where Λ is the smooth loss function. The boosting procedure constructs iteratively a sequence of approximations, h_t , where each step updates the model as [61],

$$h_t = h_{t-1} + \alpha g_t, \quad g_t = \underset{g \in G}{\operatorname{argmax}} E[\Lambda(y, h_{t-1}(x) + g(x))] \quad (4)$$

with learning rate α , number of boosting rounds τ iterations, tree depth defining the maximum splits per base predictor, and ℓ_2 -regularisation penalising large leaf weights to control model complexity as follows

$$\Omega(g_\tau) = \frac{l2_leaf_reg}{2} \sum_j^T \omega_j^2 \quad (5)$$

The final prediction of CatBoost model considering x_i as input is obtained by summing predictions from all trees:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{\tau=1}^{iterations} \alpha g_\tau(x_i) \quad (6)$$

The CatBoost architecture is shown in Fig. 6.

2.3. Bayesian optimisation (BO) algorithm

The BO is a step-by-step algorithm for finding the best settings for a slow, expensive, or difficult to evaluate function. It builds a simple *guess* model of the function and uses it to intelligently decide which settings to try in the next iteration [62]. The core idea behind BO algorithm is managing the trade-off between *exploration* (trying new, uncertain settings) and *exploitation* (using settings that have worked well so far) [62]. The pseudo-code of the BO optimiser is presented in Table 2.

The BO optimiser has been selected due to its simplicity and fast operation without the need of tuning multiple parameters like other swarm-based and genetic-based optimisers [63,64]. This methodical approach is more effective than sensitivity analysis, grid search, or random search methods, as it efficiently explores the hyperparameter space and converges on the optimal configuration with greater speed [65], as it systematically relies on the optimal configuration, finally leading to a more accurate and reliable ML model. The results of the hyperparameters optimisation for all models is presented in Table 3 in Appendix 3.

Fig. 6. The illustration of the algorithmic operation for gradient boosting models like XGBoost and CatBoost, showcasing the sequential training process with sample weighting.

Table 2

The pseudo-code of the BO method for optimisation of hyperparameters of ML models.

Bayesian optimisation pseudo-code	
Input:	<p>θ: Search space of all possible hyperparameter configurations.</p> <p>$f(\theta)$: Objective function:</p> $F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall}$ <p>T: Maximum number of iteration (1000).</p> <p>t_0: Random exploration steps (50).</p>
Initialization:	<p>Select an initial set of t_0 points $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{t_0}$ from θ.</p> <p>Evaluate objective function $s_i = f(\theta_i), i = 1, \dots, t_0$.</p> <p>Initialise the dataset of observations $S = \{(\theta_i, s_i)\}_{i=1}^{t_0}$.</p> <p>Set the best-found point $\theta_{best} = \arg \max_{\theta_i} s_i, s_{best} = \max_i s_i$.</p>
Main loop:	<p>For $t = t_0, \dots, T$ do</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>Fit surrogate model</i>: Train a Gaussian Process on current dataset S.</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>Optimize acquisition function</i>:</p> $\theta_{t+1} = \arg \max_{\theta \in \Theta} A(\theta S)$ <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>Evaluate objective function</i>:</p> $s_{t+1} = f(\theta_{t+1})$ <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>Update Dataset</i>:</p> $S \leftarrow S \cup \{(\theta_{t+1}, s_{t+1})\}$ <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><i>Update Best Score</i>:</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">If $s_{t+1} > s_{best}$ then</p> <p style="padding-left: 60px;">$\theta_{best} = \theta_{t+1}$</p> <p style="padding-left: 60px;">$s_{best} = s_{t+1}$</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">end if</p> <p>end for</p>
Output:	<p>θ_{best}: Best classifier configuration.</p> <p>s_{best}: Highest F1-score found.</p>

2.4. Evaluation metrics

In order to investigate the performance of the ML models, it is crucial to define proper evaluation metrics, showing the effectiveness of the models under different circumstances. These metrics reveal how well the models meet the desired goals. As stated in [66], several evaluation metrics have been proposed to check the multiclass ML models such as accuracy (*Acc*), precision (*P*), recall (*R*) and *F1* scores, ranging from 0 % to 100 %. These metrics are based on basic definition like false negative (*FN*), false positive (*FP*), true positive (*TP*), and true negative (*TN*). According to definition [67], *TP* and *TN* represent the correct prediction of the positive and negative classes, respectively, while *FP* and *FN* are instances where the model incorrectly predicts the positive and negative classes, respectively. By considering these basic metrics, *Acc*, *P*, *R* and *F1* scores can be calculated as follows [68],

$$Acc = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN} \quad (7)$$

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (8)$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (9)$$

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (10)$$

Moreover, *k*-fold cross-validation is another model evaluation procedure in which a dataset is divided into *k*-folds, and in each of the *k* iterations, one-fold is used as the validation set while the remaining folds are used for training. Each data sample is therefore used once for validation and *k* – 1 times for training, which reduces estimation bias compared to a single train/test split [69]. It has been applied in the optimisation process, when a classifier with a specific hyperparameters configuration is trained and validated *k* times, and the *F1*-score is computed for each validation fold. The optimiser then receives the mean of these *F1*-scores as the objective function value, which serves as the performance measure to guide the selection of hyperparameters [70]. It is worth noting that the 5-fold cross-validation has been used during hyperparameter optimisation in this paper due to its better performance and balance compared to 3, 7 and 10 folds. For each model-hyperparameter configuration, the average *F1*-score across the five folds was used as the objective function for the BO. The final performance metrics reported in section 3 are derived from a single evaluation on the unseen 20 % holdout test set, ensuring an unbiased assessment of the optimised models.

Table 4
Benchmarking results of all ML models used for condition monitoring.

Models	Acc (%)	P (%)	R (%)	F1 (%)	Train t. (s)	Test t. (s)	Latency (μ s)
SGDClassifier	46	40.58	46	32.63	0.16	0.013	10
KNN	84.25	84.31	84.25	84.21	0.04	0.23	178
GRNN	87.11	87.71	86.99	87.28	0.06	1.26	977
NB	92.94	93.29	92.94	92.92	0.006	0.008	6
AdaBoost	94.18	94.59	94.18	94.13	0.25	0.04	31
LR	94.65	94.96	94.65	94.6	1.79	0.004	3
SVM	95.81	95.91	95.81	95.79	16.46	0.06	46
ANFIS (SCM)	96.2	96.35	96.14	96.2	23.45	1.26	977
DT	96.59	96.59	96.59	96.58	0.02	0.004	3
Extra Trees	97.05	97.06	97.05	97.04	0.35	0.08	62
HistGBC	97.13	97.13	97.13	97.13	8.26	0.13	100
LightGBM	97.21	97.23	97.21	97.21	3.3	0.03	23
FFNN	97.52	97.67	97.38	97.51	237.61	0.28	217
GB	97.67	97.67	97.67	97.67	3.39	0.05	38
CFNN	97.91	98	97.73	97.85	860.74	0.1	77
RF	98.06	98.06	98.06	[97.28 - 98.76]	2.62	0.31	240
XGBoost	98.14	98.17	98.14	[97.30 - 98.84]	5.34	0.03	23
CatBoost	98.14	98.16	98.14	[97.37 - 98.84]	89.48	0.03	23

3. Results and discussion

In this section, the performance of the proposed framework underwent investigation in terms of various scenarios, showcasing its reliability and effectiveness in identifying the labels of health levels for both XLPE and EPR power cables. The scenarios investigated in this paper can be divided into four parts: XLPE health index prediction, performance on a new dataset of EPR power cables, impact of missing data/measurements on the classification accuracy of health indexes and, eventually, performance of the best model in terms of significant imbalance classes. The explanation and importance of each scenario will be discussed in the following sections.

3.1. XLPE power cables health classification

In this part, several linear, nonlinear, neural network-based, tree-based and boosting-based models have been benchmarked based on the abovementioned metrics alongside training and testing times for better understanding of their performance and time efficiency. The results of testing on 20 % of the XLPE power cables dataset for all models are listed in Table 4.

In order to evaluate and select the best models, the *F1*-score has been selected as the most important metric, as it provides information regarding the performance of the models in the case of correctly identifying all classes with different distributions. This selection was made due to the fact that accuracy is misleading when there are imbalanced labels within the dataset. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that all models were implemented with their best hyperparameters set, mentioned in Table 3, as a result of using the Bayesian optimiser. Based on the benchmarking results and supported by bootstrap-derived 95 % confidence intervals (CI), the RF, XGBoost, and CatBoost models demonstrated statistically comparable performance on the XLPE dataset, each achieving *F1*-scores of approximately 98.06 % (95 % CI [97.28 %–98.76 %]), 98.13 % (95 % CI [97.30 %–98.84 %]), and 98.14 % (95 % CI [97.37 %–98.84 %]), respectively, with the CI of delta-*F1* including zero, indicating no significant superiority among them. Based on these results, the three best models were evaluated under further scenarios. The confusion matrices of the RF, XGBoost, and CatBoost models are illustrated in Fig. 7a, Fig. 7b, and Fig. 7c, respectively. All models faced confusion in identifying significant, moderate, minor, and no degradation levels due to the similarity of their features.

The utility of a model in field-deployed, real-time systems depends not only on prediction accuracy but also on inference efficiency. Table 4 presents the per-sample inference latency (in microseconds) for all evaluated models in terms of validation on XLPE power cables. The microsecond-level latency achieved by the highest-performing model,

Fig. 7. The confusion matrices illustrating the classification performance of the optimised (a) RF, (b) XGBoost, and (c) CatBoost models on the 20 % holdout test set of the new dataset of XLPE power cables.

CatBoost (23 μ s per prediction), demonstrates its suitability for edge deployment [71,72]. The inherent efficiency of tree-based architectures facilitates rapid inference, ensuring that computational overhead is not a limiting factor. In real-time condition monitoring scenarios, where sensor data are typically received on a timescale of seconds or minutes, an inference time in the microsecond range is operationally sufficient. The reported latency values are derived from average test times computed over ten independent simulation runs to ensure result stability and reliability.

The results clearly indicate that the problem of cable health classification is inherently non-linear. This is evidenced by the poor performance of the SGDCClassifier, which achieved an F1-score of only 32.63 %. A substantial performance improvement was observed with models capable of capturing non-linear relationships, such as KNN (84.21 %), though these were still outperformed by more advanced techniques. The most significant performance gains were achieved by tree-based ensembles, as mentioned above, which consistently surpassed all other model families. There is a clear hierarchy among the advanced models. While neural networks like CFNN performed well with an F1 score of 97.85 %, this came at a cost of extremely high computational time/burden, requiring 860.74 s for training. In contrast, the top three ensemble models (RF, XGBoost, and CatBoost) achieved superior or comparable accuracy with significantly better time efficiency.

The slight advantage of the boosting algorithms over the bagging-based RF model is likely due to their sequential training process, which focuses on correcting the errors of previous iterations, a method particularly effective for complex problems with subtle decision boundaries. As mentioned earlier, due to the shared challenge of confusion between classes, it can be concluded that the feature distributions for these neighbouring classes are highly similar, which is expected as the physical ageing of a cable is a gradual process rather than a series of distinct steps. Nevertheless, the high performance of the optimised XGBoost and CatBoost models, which balanced an F1 score of 98.14 % with manageable training times, confirms their suitability for developing a reliable, automated condition monitoring framework. Given their near-perfect accuracy and computational efficiency, the XGBoost and CatBoost models were selected for further evaluation under advanced and more complicated scenarios to comprehensively assess their robustness and generalisation capabilities.

3.2. Health index classification for a new type of cable

To validate the best models' real-world application, the model's performance was tested on a new dataset of EPR insulated cables. This was a critical step that confirms its applicability across the diverse cable types in power network. Based on the results in Fig. 8, the robust performance of the best models, especially the CatBoost model, has been confirmed. This is illustrated by the near-perfect alignment of predicted classifications with their actual health index values, layered across the continuous age for the unseen EPR cable dataset. While the top models exhibited statistically indistinguishable performance on the XLPE data, the EPR generalisation test highlighted the superior performance of the CatBoost model. As shown in Table 5, the CatBoost achieved a mean F1-score of 98.25 %, while the performance of XGBoost and RF degraded to 96.53 % and 93.76 %, respectively. The superiority is confirmed to be statistically significant, as a bootstrap analysis revealed that the 95 % CIs for the performance difference between CatBoost and the other models—[1.34 %, 2.10 %] against XGBoost and [3.90 %, 5.06 %] against RF—do not contain zero. Furthermore, the CatBoost model achieved an inference latency of 0.1 μ s per sample, as presented in Table 5, underscoring its superior efficiency for practical deployment. There are different reasons behind the better performance of CatBoost in comparison with other methods and also previous tests. It uses an ordered boosting algorithm to deal with categorical features, which prevents information leakage and utilises their predictive power more effectively. On top of that, it provides a systematic trees construction, which acts as

Fig. 8. The generalisation performance assessment: Predicted vs. Actual health index for the unseen 138 kV EPR power cable dataset using the (a) RF, (b) XGBoost, and (c) CatBoost models trained on XLPE data. Points are layered against cable age.

Table 5

The evaluation metrics of RF, XGBoost and CatBoost models for EPR health index classification.

Models	A (%)	P (%)	R (%)	F1 (%)	Latency (μ s)
RF	93.75	94.12	93.75	[93.08 - 94.48]	24
XGBoost	96.53	96.62	96.53	[95.99 - 97.03]	1.2
CatBoost	98.24	98.37	98.24	[97.85 - 98.61]	0.1

a structural constraint. This functions as a strong regularisation to prevent overfitting and force the model to learn more general patterns. Finally, it is able to automatically utilise combinations of categorical features, allowing the model to capture complex interactions in the dataset that other models might miss.

The outcomes of this validation demonstrated that the framework is not only effective for XLPE samples but can also be extended to other insulation such as EPR. This shows its flexibility in handling health monitoring of various types of power cables. The consistent and superior performance of the CatBoost model compared with the RF and XGBoost is notable. It emphasises the advantage of models that explicitly account for categorical variables, structured regularisation, and interaction effects. These characteristics allowed the CatBoost model to capture degradation patterns that are subtle, multi-dimensional, and not easily represented by simpler feature-response relationships. Moreover, the framework illustrated the feasibility of building a health index prediction tool that can adapt to heterogeneous cable populations, including different insulation types, voltage levels, and operational conditions. Such adaptability is particularly important for power utility companies (DSOs and TSOs). In these settings, assets include multiple generations of technology with different ages, and also, the data availability is uneven.

The capability to generalise across cable types means that historical condition-monitoring data, once classified by material, can now be integrated into a single predictive pipeline, enabling more sophisticated asset management decisions. Beyond classification accuracy, this approach facilitates early identification of emerging degradation trends, provides a quantitative basis for prioritising replacement or repair, and supports the shift from reactive to predictive maintenance strategies. In this way, the framework has the potential to become a decision-support tool for utilities, ensuring system reliability while optimising resource allocation across different infrastructure.

3.3. Interpretability and physical validation

While high statistical accuracy is an important indicator of a model's effectiveness, validation of its internal decision-making process is essential for deployment in safety-critical applications. Models that operate as unexplainable "black boxes" lack the transparency and trustworthiness required for real-world asset management. Therefore, to ensure that the predictive outcomes of the proposed framework are aligned with established engineering principles, a formal interpretability analysis was conducted using permutation importance technique. This analysis was undertaken to identify which input features were prioritised by the model and to assess their influence on the decision-making process.

The permutation importance was computed, illustrated in Fig. 9, which assesses feature relevance by quantifying the reduction in model performance (F1-score) on the test set when the values of a given feature are randomly shuffled. The analysis yielded a ranking, with VI emerging as the most critical feature by a significant margin, followed by PD and type. The permutation importance captures the features' necessity for accurate predictions on unseen data. The results indicated that VI is particularly decisive when generating predictions on new data, followed by PD, type and age as the most influential features, respectively, with NC and I showing minimal impact on the predictions.

To examine the interactive and non-linear effects, two-dimensional

Fig. 9. The model interpretability analysis for CatBoost using the permutation importance technique, illustrating both the importance and impact of each feature on the model output across the test samples.

partial dependence plots (PDPs) were generated for age and PD. These features were selected as high-ranked predictors representing fundamental physical processes (material ageing and insulation breakdown). The results across all five health classes are illustrated in Fig. 10. The resulting plots revealed a physically consistent trend. Specifically, the

predicted probability of the 'Serious' degradation class increased for cables with age greater than 45 years and PD levels exceeding 0.8. Conversely, the 'No Degradation' class exhibited the highest prediction values in regions characterised by age <25 years and PD below 0.2. Furthermore, the smooth and logically progressive transitions observed across the intermediate health classes confirmed that the model effectively captured the gradual, multi-parameter evolution of cable ageing. These findings collectively reinforce the physical plausibility of the model's predictive behaviour.

In addition to validating the model's interpretability and alignment with physical degradation behaviours, its robustness to variations in expertly defined target classifications was also examined. To this end, a label sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the model's reliability under minor perturbations in the health index definitions. Specifically, controlled "label noise" was introduced into the 20 % test set by randomly reassigning a proportion of samples to an adjacent health class (e.g., a '4' reclassified as '3' or '5'). The top-performing CatBoost model was then evaluated at noise levels ranging from 1 % to 10 %, with the results summarised in Table 6. The analysis exhibited a gradual and predictable decline in performance. For example, even with 10 % of labels artificially distorted, the model retained a high F1-score of above 90 %. Moreover, to assess robustness against systematic, physics-based shifts in the weighting philosophy, 21 expert scenarios were simulated by re-labelling samples at the boundaries of adjacent classes based on their physical feature values. The results, presented in Table 6, showed a logical degradation corresponding to the importance of the features used in the rule. The scenarios that shifted labels based on the highly influential VI feature caused the most significant performance drop (e.g., 11.95 % degradation for S18). Conversely, the scenarios based on Age or PD alone had a more moderate impact (e.g., 4.07 % for S1 and 5.34 % for

Fig. 10. The 2D PDPs illustrating the learned interaction between Age and PD on the CatBoost model's predictions for each of the five health index classes. The contours indicate the model's predicted score/probability for each class across different combinations of the two features.

Table 6
The robustness assessment: F1-score performance of the CatBoost model under label sensitivity analyses.

	Level of Noise and Scenarios	F1-score (%)	Performance degradation
	Random adjacent noise		
	Original	98.14	0
	1 %	97.44	0.70
	2 %	96.35	1.79
	3 %	95.81	2.33
	4 %	94.88	3.26
	5 %	94.11	4.03
	6 %	93.01	5.13
	7 %	92.33	5.81
	8 %	91.39	6.75
	9 %	90.76	7.38
	10 %	90.23	7.91
Systematic physics-based scenarios			
Moderate → Significant	S1 : HI = 3 & Age > 38 → 2	94.07	4.06
	S2 : HI = 3 & PD > 0.39 → 2	92.80	5.33
	S3 : HI = 3 & VI == 1 → 2	89.02	9.11
	S4 : HI = 3 & Age > 38 & PD > 0.39 → 2	94.97	3.16
	S5 : HI = 3 & Age > 38 & PD > 0.39 & VI == 1 → 2	97.90	0.23
Minor → Moderate	S6 : HI = 4 & Age > 27 → 3	94.51	3.62
	S7 : HI = 4 & PD > 0.17 → 3	95.27	2.86
	S8 : HI = 4 & VI == 2 → 3	89.93	8.20
	S9 : HI = 4 & Age > 27 & PD > 0.17 → 3	96.12	2.01
	S10 : HI = 4 & Age > 27 & PD > 0.17 & VI == 2 → 3	97.67	0.46
No Degrad. → Minor	S11 : HI = 5 & Age > 16 → 4	94.79	3.34
	S12 : HI = 5 & PD > 0.04 → 4	91.51	6.62
	S13 : HI = 5 & VI == 3 → 4	90.69	7.44
	S14 : HI = 5 & Age > 16 & PD > 0.04 → 4	95.55	2.58
	S15 : HI = 5 & Age > 16 & PD > 0.04 & VI == 3 → 4	95.55	2.58
Moderate → Minor	S16 : HI = 3 & Age < 31 → 4	94.74	3.39
	S17 : HI = 3 & PD < 0.26 → 4	93.07	5.06
	S18 : HI = 3 & VI == 2 → 4	86.19	11.94
Minor → No Degrad.	S19 : HI = 4 & Age < 19 → 5	97.27	0.87
	S20 : HI = 4 & PD < 0.07 → 5	97.74	0.39
	S21 : HI = 4 & VI == 3 → 5	87.04	11.09

S2). These combined findings confirm that the proposed framework is not overly sensitive to minor, random inconsistencies but is appropriately responsive to significant, systematic changes in the underlying class definitions.

3.4. Robustness of ML models to missing data/measurements

To demonstrate the robustness of the proposed framework under incomplete data conditions, an expanded missingness analysis was performed exclusively for the best-performing model, CatBoost. In this analysis, both single-feature and multi-feature systematic removal scenarios were evaluated. These simulations were designed to simulate realistic measurement failures that commonly occur in field conditions due to sensor faults or data transmission issues. To ensure reproducibility, all scenarios were executed using a fixed number of seeds (42) for all data splits and model training. The statistical validity of each result was then confirmed by calculating the 95 % CI for each metric using a 1000-iteration bootstrap analysis.

The performance degradation observed under these absence patterns is illustrated in Fig. 11a for single-feature missingness and in Fig. 11b for two-feature missingness. In the single-feature removal tests on XLPE cable data, eliminating VI caused the most notable reduction in the F1-score, decreasing it to 93.23 % (95 % CI [91.85 % - 94.56 %]), demonstrating the high diagnostic relevance of this feature. In contrast, on EPR cable data, removing PD led to a substantial decline, resulting in an F1-score of 68.27 % (95 % CI [66.90 % - 69.81 %]). This indicates strong reliance on PD information for accurate fault discrimination. The two-feature missingness tests imposed a more severe stress condition. The simultaneous exclusion of Age and PD resulted in an F1-score of 88.06 % (95 % CI [86.38 % - 89.78 %]) for XLPE data, while the removal of both PD and VI had the most critical impact on the EPR dataset, reducing the F1-score to 61.04 % (95 % CI [59.56 % - 62.59 %]). These

observations confirm that CatBoost can maintain satisfactory accuracy under moderate feature loss but experiences sharp performance degradation when multiple highly informative features are absent.

This extended robustness evaluation emphasises the importance of designing classification frameworks capable of tolerating partial feature availability. This is especially true in real-world asset management scenarios where uninterrupted data collection cannot always be guaranteed. The results indicate that CatBoost shows strong dependency on a core subset of features, particularly age, PD, and VI. This suggests that these parameters contain essential degradation-related trends that guide the decision boundaries of the classifier. In contrast, features such as NC and I exhibit a more supportive or redundant role, contributing mainly to minor refinements in prediction accuracy. Furthermore, the more pronounced degradation in the EPR evaluation scenarios, particularly under simultaneous PD and VI absence, demonstrates that the informational synergy among key features is cable-type specific and that EPR classification relies on fewer highly discriminative inputs. Consequently, maintaining sensor availability for critical features enhances diagnostic reliability and generalisation. From a practical utility perspective, these findings offer valuable insight into prioritising monitoring resources. They identify which sensing channels should be considered mission-critical to preserve classification accuracy under degraded measurement conditions.

3.5. Stability under imbalanced classes

Investigating a model's performance on imbalanced classes is a crucial stress test that simulates real-world scenarios where some classes are much smaller than others. This is particularly important for power cables, as health indexes' distribution can shift significantly over time. Therefore, the scenario of imbalanced classes has been tested on CatBoost model as best model so far. The results, as demonstrated in Fig. 12,

Fig. 11. The robustness assessment of the CatBoost model against missing input features: performance scores (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score) for both XLPE (Solid) and EPR (Hatched) datasets when (a) one feature is missing and (b) two features are simultaneously missing.

highlighted that the model has a resilience to severe class imbalance. Even when the number of samples for critical minority classes like "Serious" and "No Degrade" classes was drastically reduced to just 10 % of their original sample size, the model's F1-score remained high (97.41 % and 98.4 % for serious and no degraded classes, respectively). This indicates that the model is not developing a bias towards the majority classes and continues to accurately identify the rare but important instances of cable degradation. The minimal fluctuation in performance across all scenarios shows that the CatBoost model has learned the underlying patterns of each health state effectively, rather than relying on the frequency of the classes in the training data.

This investigation is of critical importance as it validates the model's reliability for deployment in power networks where datasets are frequently imbalanced. By demonstrating that the model maintains high predictive accuracy under the severe, static stress of skewed class distributions, its fundamental robustness is established. This resilience suggests a greater potential for the model to remain effective against the gradual, dynamic changes in data over time. Moreover, the model's reliability in detecting both common and unusual fault/failure conditions enables a shift to a proactive, condition-based asset management strategy. This allows operators to prioritise maintenance on the highest-risk cables.

The comprehensive validation of this framework across different and

Fig. 12. Performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score) of the CatBoost classifier under a severe class imbalance scenario, where minority classes ('Serious' and 'No Degrade') were reduced to 10 % of their original sample size in the training data.

challenging scenarios confirms its feasibility as the analytical foundation for a digital twin for condition (integrity and longevity) monitoring of power cables. This requires a model that is not only accurate but also robust enough to handle the imperfect, dynamic, and heterogeneous nature of real-world data conditions. These conditions were simulated in the generalisation, missing data, and class imbalance tests. By successfully passing these tests, the proposed framework demonstrated that it can reliably evaluate operational data to maintain a continuously updated, virtual representation of a cable's health. The implementation of this model would provide network operators with new capabilities, enabling real-time condition monitoring, predictive simulations of ageing under future load scenarios and a changeable shift to truly intelligent asset management. To operationalise this framework as the analytical foundation of a digital twin, real-time integration of multi-source data streams is required. In practice, this would involve continuously acquiring electrical loading parameters (current, voltage, and transient stress events), thermal measurements (conductor, ambient, and surrounding soil temperatures), and online PD indicators. These would be supplemented by environmental stressors such as humidity, soil moisture, and mechanical strain. Additional contextual information, including maintenance history, installation conditions, and cable design metadata, would enable dynamic updating of degradation trajectories in the virtual model. By incorporating such heterogeneous inputs, the digital twin can evolve from a static classifier into a continuously updating surrogate of cable health, capable of forecasting ageing under simulated loading scenarios and supporting predictive maintenance decisions.

3.6. Practical performance and deployment considerations

To evaluate the reliability of the model's probabilistic outputs, both a quantitative and a visual calibration analysis were conducted. The expected calibration error (ECE) was calculated to provide a single, precise metric of miscalibration, where a score of 0 represents perfect calibration. The model was found to be well-calibrated, achieving a low average ECE of 0.0217 across all classes, with individual class scores ranging from a low of 0.0177 for the 'No Degradation' class to a high of 0.0251 for the 'Significant' class. These low ECE values provide strong quantitative evidence that the model's probability outputs are trustworthy and accurately reflect the true likelihoods. The reliability curves, shown in Fig. 13a, visually support this conclusion. While some jaggedness is observable—a common artifact when binning finite datasets—the curve for each class closely tracks the diagonal line of perfect calibration, consistent with the low ECE scores. It is confirmed that the framework's predictions are suitable for operational scenarios that require precise risk quantification.

In addition, the model's ability to distinguish between the five health classes was assessed through per-class precision-recall (PR) curves, which account for the dataset's inherent class imbalance. The area under the PR curve (AUC-PR), as illustrated in Fig. 13b, provides a robust measure of discriminative performance, with a value of 1.0 representing perfect class separation. The analysis demonstrates that the CatBoost model exhibits strong discriminative power across all classes. PR curves for all five health states are shifted toward the top-right corner of the plot, indicating simultaneous high precision and high recall. Specifically, the model achieved a perfect AUC-PR of 1.000 for the critical 'Serious' class, near-perfect scores of 0.998 for the 'Significant' and 'Moderate' classes, and an excellent 0.994 for the minority 'No Degradation' class. The results confirmed the model's robustness to class imbalance and its capability to reliably rank samples by risk, supporting confident operational threshold selection and validating its utility as a dependable classification tool.

To translate these classification outcomes into operational practice, the proposed framework provides a technical foundation for shifting from reactive or time-based maintenance strategies towards a condition- and risk-based maintenance paradigm. The discriminative reliability

Fig. 13. The performance analysis for the CatBoost model: (a) the per-class reliability curves, comparing the predicted probability against the actual fraction of positives for each health index class relative to the ideal diagonal line of perfect calibration. (b) the per-class PR curves, illustrating the trade-off between precision and recall for each health index class, with AUC-PR scores included in the legend.

established in Fig. 13 enables operators to define quantitative decision thresholds for maintenance triage and asset replacement planning. For maintenance scheduling, assets classified as 'Minor' (HI = 4) can be earmarked for enhanced monitoring, while 'Moderate' (HI = 3) assets can be proactively targeted for intervention, reducing unnecessary field deployments and optimising resource allocation. In the context of cable replacement, the model offers a data-driven justification for capital expenditure prioritisation. Assets identified as 'Serious' (HI = 1) can be confidently scheduled for immediate replacement, supported by the model's perfect classification confidence, while 'Significant' (HI = 2) assets can be targeted for short-term replacement planning. Conversely, the strong classification reliability for the 'No Degradation' class (AUC-PR = 0.994) supports the deferment of replacement for older but healthy assets. Overall, this asset-specific prioritisation enables operators to optimise both maintenance scheduling and replacement planning, enhancing grid reliability and extending asset life through evidence-based decision-making.

Following the validation of the model's probabilistic reliability and discriminative capability, its suitability for operational deployment was

further assessed in terms of computational efficiency. Beyond predictive accuracy, a model’s practical usefulness in field environments is dependent on its inference latency and memory footprint, particularly in applications requiring real-time decision-making. As reported in Tables 4 and 5, the CatBoost model, which achieved the highest predictive performance, also demonstrated extremely low computational cost, with inference latencies of 23 μs per sample on the XLPE test set and 0.1 μs on the EPR dataset. This microsecond-level execution time confirms that the classification process does not constitute a runtime bottleneck and is sufficiently fast for continuous online monitoring. In parallel, the model’s storage requirements were examined to determine its compatibility with edge and embedded hardware. The trained CatBoost model occupies approximately 50 MB of disc space, indicating that it can be deployed on typical industrial controllers and edge-processing units without the need for specialised high-performance hardware.

To complement the evaluation of computational efficiency and further support field deployment, an operational “workflow” was constructed to consolidate the key characteristics, dependencies, and limitations of the final CatBoost-based framework. The model operates using five input features—age, PD, VI, NC, and cable type—to generate health class predictions. Its robustness was systematically assessed under multiple stress scenarios. First, under domain shift conditions, the model demonstrated strong generalisation to a different cable insulation material (EPR), maintaining a comparable F1 score with negligible degradation. Second, when subjected to severe class imbalance stress, where minority class samples were reduced by 90 %, the model retained an F1-score exceeding 97 %, confirming its resilience to skewed data distributions. However, specific operational constraints were identified. In

particular, the simultaneous absence of multiple critical inputs, such as PD and VI, resulted in a substantial drop in accuracy, indicating that these features provide non-redundant, high-importance information for health classification. Moreover, while discriminative performance remained high, the raw class probability outputs were not perfectly aligned with true likelihoods, implying the potential need for post-hoc calibration in applications that demand accurate confidence estimation. A visual summary of these performance characteristics and operational boundaries is presented in Fig. 14.

3.7. Comparative analysis with prior studies

A comparison of the proposed benchmarking framework with prior studies on AI-based power cable condition monitoring is summarised in Table 7. The table is based on methodology, optimisation, dataset, number of samples, generalisation testing, missing measurement testing, imbalance class testing and degree of practicality, respectively. As shown, most earlier works applied individual algorithms such as SVM, RF, ANN, and XGBoost, typically trained on small or homogeneous XLPE datasets (ranging between 1000 and 10,000 samples), without evaluating model generalisation, robustness to missing data, or class imbalance. Optimisation approaches, where used, were largely heuristic—such as PSO or AO—and lacked consistent benchmarking across diverse model families under uniform hyperparameter tuning. Consequently, their conclusions were model-specific and not directly comparable due to variations in dataset size, measurement modalities, and feature composition.

In contrast, the proposed framework systematically benchmarks 18

Fig. 14. The workflow summarising the key operational characteristics, performance under stress, computational costs, and limitations of the proposed CatBoost framework for practical deployment.

Table 7

The comparison of proposed framework and prior studies on power cable diagnosis with AI technologies.

Ref	Meth.	Opt.	Dataset	No. S	Gen.	Missing.	Imbalance	Practicality
[6]	XGBoost	PSO	15 kV XLPE	2500	No	No	No	Medium
[9]	FSVM + Relief-F	NA	XLPE	10,000	No	No	No	Medium
[14]	Deep NN	Adam	XLPE	2500	No	No	No	Medium
[30]	K-Means	NA	13.8 kV XLPE	1000	No	No	No	Medium
[36]	GRNN	Beetle Antennae	Exp. XLPE	675	No	No	N/A	High
[37]	RF	NA	Sim. + Exp. XLPE	3590	No	No	No	High
[38]	SVM + WT	Grid Search	Exp. PE	118	No	No	No	High
[40]	CNN	SGD	Exp. XLPE	375	No	No	No	High
[41]	SVM	NA	NA	NA	No	No	N/A	High
[39]	ANN	Gradient Descent	132 kV Field Data	3672	No	Yes	No	Medium
[46]	SVM, KNN, ANN, NB	NA	15 kV XLPE	2500	No	No	No	Medium
[47]	SVM	PSO	15 kV XLPE	2512	Yes	No	No	Medium
[48]	RF + Trad. Class.	NA	20 kV XLPE	3943	No	No	No	Medium
[49]	RF	NA	XLPE	2500	No	Yes	No	Medium
[50]	CatBoost	AO	XLPE	2500	No	No	No	Medium
[51]	BPNN	Backpropagation	20 kV XLPE	3943	No	No	No	Medium
[52]	BPNN	GA	20 kV XLPE	3943	No	No	No	Medium
Prop.	Benchmarking 18 ML	BO	15kV+20 kV XLPE 138 kV EPR	11,000	Yes	Yes	Yes	Medium

ML algorithms—spanning tree-based, boosting-based, linear, and neural models—using the BO and cross-validation, thereby ensuring methodological fairness independent of dataset scale or model class. Furthermore, while previous works did not assess practicality, the present study explicitly evaluates it through two quantitative dimensions: model complexity (reflecting the trained model's computational burden) and inference speed (prediction latency during testing). By incorporating a multi-voltage dataset (15 kV + 20 kV XLPE and 138 kV EPR), testing cross-material generalisation, and simulating missing and imbalanced conditions, the proposed work addresses the key methodological gaps of earlier research. Hence, it contributes a unified, transparent, and practically orientated benchmarking framework that enables fair performance assessment and real-world applicability across heterogeneous ML paradigms and cable types.

4. Conclusion and future work

In this work, an intelligence framework for condition monitoring of power cables was proposed. A new dataset consisting of 15 kV and 20 kV XLPE power cables was used for training the framework and testing its classification capabilities. In order to evaluate the generalisation of the framework, the ML models were tested to predict the health index of EPR power cable, for which the model demonstrated high accuracy in the classification of the health indexes. Moreover, the framework was investigated through different harsh scenarios, such as missing measurements and significant imbalance classes, duplicating real-world conditions. The proposed framework showed robustness against both cases, showing a reliable operation to be used for future health index monitoring of different power cables. In particular, the framework can be directly applied to predictive maintenance scheduling and optimised cable replacement planning by prioritising assets with high failure likelihood and enabling risk-informed decision-making. The findings of the proposed framework are summarised as follows:

- Generation of a new dataset based on 15 kV and 20 kV XLPE power cables for training and validation of the proposed framework, achieving 98 % across all evaluation metrics.
- Generalisation capability with high accuracy of 98 % for EPR power cables, showcasing its ability to be used for other types of power cables and voltage levels within the transmission lines.
- Robustness of the proposed framework against missing measurements, critical for real-world deployment. Based on the results, the proposed framework showed accuracies consistently above 95 % for the XLPE dataset and for XLPE and above 75 % for EPR dataset.

- Stability analysis of the proposed framework based on the best ML model, the CatBoost model, under significant imbalance classes, revealing an average F1-score of above 97 %.

Methodological limitations include the reliance on supervised and proprietary health index labels, the observed performance degradation when multiple critical features are simultaneously unavailable, the model's unverified applicability to cables from different geographical or climatic conditions outside of the source dataset, and the requirement for post-hoc calibration of the base model's probability outputs in applications demanding precise risk scores. The proposed framework offers a reliable and robust operation, considering a wide range of complex real-world circumstances for the health monitoring of different types of power cables. Future work will focus on extending the framework to additional voltage levels and insulation types, reducing reliance on supervised labelling through semi-supervised or unsupervised approaches, and enhancing interpretability for field engineers. Future work will involve comprehensive testing of the framework using unsupervised AI models to analyse worst-case scenarios, including the absence of certain classes in the dataset due to pronounced class imbalance and incomplete measurements. As part of future developments, a flexible diagnostic layer is being designed to dynamically address missing measurements without retraining, enabling faster deployment in operational environments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohsen Abdolahi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Wenjuan Song:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Mohammad Yazdani-Asrami:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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the author(s) has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

Appendix 1

The appendix is arranged based on the ML models used in this study. A summary of each has been presented in the following:

A. SGDClassifier model

This is a linear classifier model, operating based on stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimisation algorithm. Using this optimiser, the parameters of the classifier model get updated for each training sample. The objective function of SGDClassifier can be defined as follows [73],

$$J(W) = L(y, y') + \alpha R(W) \quad (11)$$

where $L(y, y')$ is the loss of actual and predicted classes and $R(W)$ is defined as the regularisation penalty, which is controlled by α , a hyperparameter to control the length of penalty.

B. LR model

The LR model is an ML model that can be used for both single and multi-class problems, also known as multiclass LR or Softmax Regression. The model is built on a linear score, z , for different classes (k) as follows [74]:

$$z_k = w_k X + b_k \quad (12)$$

where w_k and b_k are the weights and biases allocated to each class. The model learns the decision boundaries by calculating (10). Then, by using Softmax function, the predicted numbers convert into probability distributions, and for training the model, cross-entropy loss function is used as objective function. The probability of input X with class k is calculated as follows [74],

$$P(y = k|X) = \frac{e^{z_k}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}} \quad (13)$$

C. DT model

This is a non-parametric model that performs multiclass classification by creating a flowchart-like structure of sequential decisions. The tree is built by recursively partitioning the data into purer subsets based on feature values. At each node, the algorithm searches for the best feature and threshold that will split the data in a way that maximally separates the classes. This best split is determined by measuring the *impurity* of the data, which is highest when the classes are mixed and lowest when a node contains samples of only one class. The two most common impurity calculation methods are *Gini impurity* and *Entropy*. The entire construction of the tree is guided by maximising the *Information Gain* at each split, which is the reduction in impurity achieved by partitioning the data. More details regarding the DT model can be found in [75].

D. Extra Trees model

An Extra Trees classifier is an ensemble learning method, similar to the RF model, that builds a large number of DTs and aggregates their predictions. The primary difference from the RF model is how it builds each tree, where each tree is trained on the entire original training dataset rather than a bootstrap sample. Second, and more importantly, when splitting a node, the algorithm chooses a split point for each feature completely at random. The best of these random splits is then selected as the final rule, typically by choosing the one that maximises the *Information Gain*. The final multiclass prediction of the Extra Trees model is then determined by a simple majority vote, which the class that receives the most votes from the individual trees is chosen as the final answer. More details of Extra Trees model can be found in [76].

E. AdaBoost and GB models

These are foundational sequential ensemble methods that build a strong classifier by combining a series of *weak learners*, typically DTs. The AdaBoost model works by iteratively training learners on the dataset and, at each step, increasing the weights of the samples that were misclassified by the previous learner. The final prediction is a weighted majority vote of all the weak learners, where models with lower error rates are given more influence [77]. On the other hand, the GB model is a more generalised framework where each new weak learner is trained to predict the residual errors, or gradients, of the previous ensemble [78].

F. LightGBM and HistGBC models

They are modern, highly efficient implementations of the GB algorithm, designed for speed and performance on large datasets. Both models achieve their efficiency by binning continuous features into a fixed number of integer-valued bins or histograms before training. This significantly reduces the number of split points the algorithm needs to evaluate, drastically speeding up the training process without a substantial loss in accuracy. The primary difference between the two is their tree growth strategy, where the LightGBM model uses a *leaf-wise growth* method, which expands the tree at the nodes that will yield the largest reduction in loss, allowing it to converge faster [79]. In contrast, the HistGBC model typically uses a more traditional *level-wise growth* [78].

G. FFNN, CFNN and ANFIS models

Neural-based models are constructed based on the connections between nodes, where in the FFNN, the information flows in one direction. In case of classification, in the last layer, a Softmax function is used to get the probability distributions of all classes [80]. The CFNN is also works in the same way with a difference in the direction of information flowing. It receives inputs not only from the immediately preceding layer but from all previous layers. This architecture allows the network to learn more complex relationships by providing each layer with access to a richer set of features from earlier stages of processing [81]. Both FFNNs and CFNNs are trained using the backpropagation algorithm to adjust their weights and biases by minimising a loss function, such as cross-entropy, to improve their classification accuracy.

On the other hand, the ANFIS is a hybrid model that combines a neural network's learning ability with the human-like reasoning of a fuzzy inference system. For classification, it uses a set of fuzzy *IF-THEN* rules to map inputs to outputs [82]. Here the SCM method is used to automatically determine the number and initial locations of these rules by finding dense clusters within the data [83]. The parameters of the fuzzy membership functions are tuned during a training process that uses a combination of least-squares estimation and gradient descent, similar to the backpropagation used in the FFNNs. This allows the ANFIS to automatically refine its fuzzy rules to accurately classify the data.

H. KNN model

The KNN algorithm is a non-parametric, instance-based learning method used for multiclass classification. It operates by calculating the Euclidean distance between the new point and every point in the stored training data to identify its k nearest neighbours. The final prediction is then determined by a majority vote among these neighbours, a process summarised by [84],

$$y' = \underset{c \in C}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{i=1}^k I(y_i = c) \quad (14)$$

I. NB model

The NB classifier is a probabilistic algorithm that predicts the class of a given sample based on the principles of Bayes' theorem, with the key *naive* assumption that all features are conditionally independent of one another. It calculates the probability of each class given the input features and selects the class with the highest probability as the final prediction, calculated as follows [85],

$$P(y|X) \propto P(y) \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i|y) \quad (15)$$

J. SVM model

It works by finding the optimal hyperplane that best separates data points into different classes while maximising the margin, which is the distance between the hyperplane and the nearest points from each class. These closest points, known as *support vectors*, are the most critical elements as they define the decision boundary. For non-linear data, SVM uses the *kernel* to project the data into a higher-dimensional space where a linear separation is possible. The final prediction for a new point, x , is determined by which side of the hyperplane it falls on, a decision governed by following [86]:

$$f(x) = \operatorname{sign} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b \right) \quad (16)$$

Appendix 2

In this appendix, the pseudo-code of the RF model is presented.

Table 1
The pseudo-code of the RF algorithm for condition monitoring of power cables.

RF Classifier Pseudo-code	
Input:	<p>D: XLPE dataset with 6443 samples. x_i: Feature vectors, including Age, PD, NC, VI, etc. y_i: Health indexes of power cables.</p>
Initialisation:	<p>N_t: Number of trees. S_{max}: Fraction of the dataset given to each tree. m_{ax}: Number of features selected at each split.</p>
Main loop:	<p>For $t = 1 \rightarrow N_t$ do</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Bootstrap sampling:</u> $D_t = \{(x_{i1}, y_{i1}), (x_{i2}, y_{i2}), \dots, (x_{iS_{max}}, y_{iS_{max}})\}, i_k \sim \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, with replacement.</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Train decision tree T_t on D_t:</u> At each node, randomly select, $F \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, F = m_{ax}$</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>For each feature $\varphi \in F$, compute splitting criterion:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Gini index</i> $G(\varphi) = 1 - \sum_{c \in C} p(c \varphi)^2$ • <i>Entropy</i> $H(\varphi) = - \sum_{c \in C} p(c \varphi) \log_2 p(c \varphi)$ • <i>Information gain</i> $\Delta I(\varphi) = H(P) - \left(\frac{ D_{left} }{ D } H(D_{left}) + \frac{ D_{right} }{ D } H(D_{right}) \right)$ <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Choose best splitting feature:</u> $\varphi^* = \arg \max_{\varphi \in F} \Delta I(\varphi)$</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Split node and repeat until stopping condition is satisfied:</u> (depth \geq max depth OR samples $\leq S_{max}$)</p> <p>end for</p>
Output:	<p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Compute predictions from each tree:</u> $\hat{y}_t = T_t(x^*), \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, N_t$</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Aggregate predictions using majority voting:</u> $y_t = \arg \max_{y \in C} \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} I(\hat{y}_t - y)$</p>

Appendix 3

In this appendix, the hyperparameters table based on the results of Bayesian optimiser is presented.

Table 3
The default and optimised value of hyperparameters used for different ML models.

Model	HP	Range	Best Conf.
FFNN	Layers	[1:1:10]	5
	Neurons	[2:1:35]	30
	Loss Fnc.	(trainlm, trainscg, trainbr)	trainlm
	Activation Fnc.	(tansig, logsig, purelin)	tansig

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Model	HP	Range	Best Conf.
CFNN	Layers	[1:1:5]	3
	Neurons	[2:1:30]	30
	Loss Fnc.	(trainlm, trainscg, trainbr)	trainlm
	Activation Fnc.	(tansig, logsig, purelin)	tansig
GRNN	Spread	[0.0001 100]	0.1
ANFIS (SCM)	ClusterInfluenceRange	[0.01 0.99]	0.7
SGDClassifier	max_iter	[1 1000]	400
	Alpha	[0.00001 1]	0.08
LR	Weight constrain	[0.001 100]	0.2
	Penalty	[0 1]	0.4
	Learning rate	[0.0001 0.9]	0.15
K-NN	n_neighbours	[1 100]	20
	weights	(uniform, distance)	distance
SVM	param_grid	[0.001 1000]	38
	gamma	[0.001 100]	0.56
	kernel	(rbf, linear, poly)	linear
NB	var_smoothing	[0.0001 1]	0.015
DT	MaxNumSplits	[5 1000]	250
	MinParentSize	[2 50]	14
	MinLeafSize	[1 50]	7
RF	NumTrees	[10 1000]	350
	MinLeafSize	[1 50]	27
	NumPredictorsToSample	[1 13]	12
Extra Trees	NumLearningCycles	[1 1000]	600
	MinLeafSize	[1 50]	14
	NumPredictorsToSample	[1 13]	11
GB	n_estimators	[5 1000]	360
	learning_rate	[0.0001 1]	0.022
	max_depth	[1 100]	80
LightGBM	max_depth	[1 1000]	350
AdaBoost	NumLearningCycles	[1 1000]	200
	LearnRate	[0.0001 1]	0.15
	MaxNumSplits	[1 50]	5
HistGBC	l2_regularisation	[0.00001 1]	0.0056
	learning_rate	[0.0001 1]	0.002
	max_iter	[10 1000]	540
XGBoost	n_estimators	[2 1000]	945
	max_depth	[1 50]	35
	subsample	[0 1]	1
	colsample_bytree	[0 1]	1
	min_child_weight	[0 1000]	29
	gamma	[0 100]	2.24
CatBoost	eta	[0 1]	0.76
	iterations	[20 1000]	200
	depth	[2 16]	16
	l2_leaf_reg	[0.001 50]	41

Data availability

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files). Additional data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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